

Hypoxia-Induced Changes of Cochlear Operating Points Assessed by Low-Frequency Biased Otoacoustic Emissions and Round Window Cochlear Potentials

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Abstract. Low-frequency biasing tones have been extensively used in the past to estimate the operating point of the active cochlea. Here, using anaesthetized gerbils, we synchronously observed the modulation of DPOAE, SFOAE, CM, and CAP by a 60-Hz biasing tone (85 dB SPL) aiming to analyze operating point shifts induced by 30 seconds of hypoxia. The time course of the perturbed blood oxygenation (SpO₂) was monitored with an oximeter. Pronounced changes in the modulation pattern and overall levels of OAEs as well intermodulation products in the CM signal have been observed. However, the CAP modulation pattern remained unchanged. The overall amplitude of CAP, CM, SFOAE and the 2f₁-f₂ DPOAE component followed the SpO₂ readings, all fully recovering after ~1 minute of resuming breathing fresh air. Their modulation patterns, however, and most notably, the overall level of the f₂-f₁ component did not return to their pre-hypoxia states for a further 2 minutes. Two repetitions of the experiment over a three-hour period showed almost identical traces. While DP changes in OAE and CM can be explained by changes in the operating point (OP) along a sigmoidal nonlinearity, SFOAE and CAP modulation patterns were not useful for monitoring OP changes.

DETERMINING THE OPERATING POINT FROM DISTORTION PRODUCTS

The term cochlear operating point (OP) usually refers to the center position (average position) around which the hair bundles oscillate during acoustic stimulation. This mechanical position determines the electrical conductance of the mechano-electrical transducer (MET) channels residing at their tip. Dependent on their membrane potential, the outer hair cells (OHC) change their length, and this changes the average hair bundle angle and thus the MET OP.

Although the detailed mechanisms are still debated, there is consensus that the OHC control cochlear gain and the MET OP is likely to play an important role in this. An abnormal OP is likely to lead to hearing loss or indicates other causes of hearing loss. Thus, estimating the OP may have diagnostic relevance and might provide the ability to track fluctuating hearing loss [1].

Note that there are other compressive non-linearities in the cochlea to which the following principles apply. But for simplicity, let us assume here it is the non-linearity of the MET's input-output function (i.e., hair bundle angle to MET conductance), which is shown in Figure 1a. This 2nd-order Boltzmann function has the typical shape of a hair cell's MET functions. Illustrated below the MET function is an input signal of the hair bundle displacement (Figure 1b), consisting of two beating tones. Due to the saturating nonlinearity, the tones inter-modulate so that the spectrum of the current through the METs contains spectral components in addition to the two primary tones, so called distortion products (DPs, Figure 1e). Via the receptor potential, this current controls fast somatic electromotility in OHCs, and it is therefore not surprising that these DPs can not only be seen in the electrical potentials recorded at the round window (RW), the so-called cochlear microphonics (CM), but are also present in the pressure field of the ear canal where they are called distortion product otoacoustic emissions (DPOAE).

If a DC bias is added to the input signal (i.e., the OP is changed by changing the horizontal position of the signal in Figure 1b), the strength of the two DPs change deterministically and in the opposite way (Figure 1e): Where the even-order DP, f₂-f₁ (red), has its maximum strength, the odd-order DP, 2f₁-f₂ (blue), has a notch, and vice versa.

Figure 1f schematically illustrates the generation of the two types of DPOAE and their dependence on the OP along a "hard" saturating non-linear function that simply "clips" the signal when it exceeds its range. The difference

tone $f_2 - f_1$ is large when the OP does not sit in the middle of the function and the signal is clipped asymmetrically (upper and lower panel). It has the frequency of the beat as it follows the short-term average of the signal (red line). If the OP sits in the middle of the function, the signal gets clipped symmetrically and the short-time average remains zero throughout. However, the signal amplitude is periodically reduced by clipping (blue arrows). In other words, it is amplitude modulated at the beat frequency ($f_2 - f_1$), and this explains the modulation sideline in the output spectrum neighboring f_1 , at $f_1 - (f_2 - f_1) = 2f_1 - f_2$, and f_2 , at $f_2 + (f_2 - f_1) = 2f_2 - f_1$. The two other modulation sidelines, $f_1 + (f_2 - f_1) = f_2$ and $f_2 - (f_2 - f_1) = f_1$, coincide with the f_1 and f_2 primary stimulus tones and can therefore not be observed directly. In the ear canal, the $2f_1 - f_2$ DPOAE is usually the largest and is therefore preferably used as a diagnostic marker in the clinic.

FIGURE 1. Theory of operating point analysis (DPOAE)

SFOAE BIASING

As the strength of DPOAEs depends on various factors, the position of the OP can only be determined by comparing the strength between odd and even DPOAEs. Unfortunately, the $f_2 - f_1$ is in the human ear often buried in the noise. If, however, one of the stimulus tones' frequency is chosen much smaller than the other ($f_1 < f_2/10$), the

output spectrum contains even and odd DPs that are spectrally very close to the higher stimulus tone, with the advantage that they are influenced by very similar transfer characteristics to the ear canal (Figure 2c,d). The data can be interpreted as modulated stimulus-frequency otoacoustic emissions (SFOAE). SFOAE are cochlear reflections in response to a single primary tone, f_p . The lower frequency tone is often called the “biasing” tone (f_{BT}) as it biases periodically the position of the cochlear partition, which leads to a modulation of the reflection that can be seen as modulation side-lines either side of f_p . As these reflections depend on active OHC electromotility, one might assume that the modulation characteristics also depend on the OP position along their MET. The theoretical dependence of the modulation sideline amplitudes on the OP along the sigmoidal MET function in Figure 1a is illustrated schematically in Figure 2a, and a schematic explanation with the hard-clipping input-output function is given in Figure 2b: In the upper and lower panel, the signal is clipped asymmetrically and so reductions in amplitude occur once per biasing cycle, giving rise to the modulation side-line pair, $f_p - f_{BT}$ and $f_p + f_{BT}$ (even DPs, red). When the signal is clipped symmetrically (middle), reductions in amplitude occur twice per biasing cycle, giving rise to the modulation side-line pair, $f_p - 2f_{BT}$ and $f_p + 2f_{BT}$ (even DPs, blue). The side-lines can be observed in both, the spectrum of recordings made in the ear canal and with a RW recording electrode when the primary tone biased with a 60 Hz tone of 85 dB SPL (Figure 2 c and 2d, respectively). The purpose of the current study was to explore whether the relative strength of these side-line pairs can be used to non-invasively infer the cochlear OP.

FIGURE 2. Theory of operating point analysis (biased SFOAE) and experimental data

DPOAE BIASING

To do so, we compared the novel SFOAE method with a more traditional way to determine the cochlear OP, where DPOAE generation is modulated with a third tone, which acts as a biasing tone^{1,2,3}. Figures 3a and c show the spectra of ear canal and RW recording, respectively. Figures 3b and 3d show the amplitude modulation patterns not only of

the f_2 - f_1 (red) and $2f_1$ - f_2 (blue) DPOAE, but also for the SFOAE (black) that were reconstructed from the (complex-valued) spectra shown in Figures 2c and 2d. (The black dotted line in Figures 3b&d is the biasing tone waveform. Unmodulated levels are shown by dashed lines.) The theoretical behavior of the relevant spectral lines with changing OP is shown in Figure 3e. Amplitude changes of inner (crosses) and outer (dots) side-line pairs are again of opposite direction so that the OP can be determined theoretically when analyzing either f_2 - f_1 or $2f_1$ - f_2 modulations separately, without knowledge of the overall DPOAE amplitude or modulation depth.

As with SFOAE biasing, modulation sidelines are spectrally close to the DPs themselves and should undergo similar transformations when travelling out to the ear canal. However, some complication is likely here because the nicely strong $2f_1$ - f_2 DPOAE can travel from the DP generation place near the best place of f_2 both directly back to the ear canal, and more indirectly after first travelling more apically to its own best place, where it is reflected similarly to an SFOAE. Due to the difference in travel time, both parts arrive in the ear canal superimposed with unknown phase relationship, so can strengthen, or partially cancel each other. They might also be differently modulated by the biasing tone. This could make the interpretation of these spectral lines less reliable than those of modulated SFOAEs.

Figure 3f shows the modulation of the amplitude compound action potential (CAP) by the biasing tone. (The symmetrized black envelope indicates the peak-to-peak amplitude, and the pink trace* on the left is the unbiased CAP). This was made possible by the design of our stimulus complex, consisting of 39 stimulus intervals of 125 ms duration that contained various combinations of f_1 -, f_2 -, biasing-, and SFOAE-suppressor-tones (Figure 4). The f_2 -tone always started before any f_1 -, or SFOAE-suppressor tones, and in such a way that 4 of the 32 onsets during the biasing tone exposure were located at each of 8 equidistant phase positions of the biasing tone. Two of these four had inverted

FIGURE 3. Experimental data of biased DPOAE.

polarity. During the first 1 second of the stimulus complex the biasing tone was off, and the presentation of 7 intervals allowed for the measurement of the unbiased DPOAE, SFOAE, and CAP. For the remaining 5 seconds, the biasing tone was switched on continuously with 125-ms raised-cosine ramps.

OPERATING POINT CHANGES INDUCED BY HYPOXIA

In Figure 5, we show one example of hypoxia-induced OP shifts recorded from a gerbil ear. Anesthesia was introduced and maintained with a mix of ketamine/xylazine, administered continuously by a syringe pump and monitored via pedal reflex. (All procedures were performed under Home Office PPL PP2468747.) The stimulus complex was repeated continuously during OP monitoring, permitting data sampling at 6-s intervals.

FIGURE 4. The 6-s stimulus complex consisted of 39 stimulus intervals.

FIGURE 5. Changes in spectral magnitudes induced by 30 seconds of hypoxia.

The vertical blue bar indicates the time for which the spectra and modulation patterns are shown in the previous figures. The time was chosen because most of the modulation patterns were pronounced and clear. (At other times, many were overmodulated, others hardly modulated.) During the first 3 minutes, spectra were checked for stability. At time 0:00 (left green bar), the animal was partially starved of oxygen by extending its tracheotomy tube with a 1-ml syringe outer tube (so the animal breathed in the same air that it had just breathed out) utilizing a motorized translation stage (see artifact in the electrical recordings). Figure 5a shows that the blood oxygen level (SpO₂) started to drop immediately and appears to level off just before fresh air was supplied again after 30 seconds. SpO₂ recovered rapidly and exhibited a slight overshoot.

DP carrier tones and their modulation side-lines reacted to the hypoxia with a ~20-s delay and continued to change for approximately 3 min, after fresh air supply had resumed. (Panels b-f; Solid lines are carrier levels. Lines with crossed and dotted markers are inner and outer modulation line levels, respectively.) The direction of these changes reversed after ~50 s. By tracing left and right the theoretical levels in Figure 5h (a copy of Figure 3e), thereby trying to capture the ups and downs in the spectral lines of both, 2f₁-f₂ (blue) and f₂-f₁ (red) DPOAE in figure 5b, the time course of the OP during and following hypoxia was estimated by eye (Figure 5g). The time course of OP shifts derived from the CM (Figure 5c) would be similar, but smaller (not illustrated). As the RW-recorded CM stems from a more basal cochlear location than the DPOAE, it is possible that the OP shifts were smaller there, and the start position was different.

OP shifts from the modulated SFOAE could not be obtained. The overall amplitude of the SFOAE decreased by >15 dB (Figure 5d) during hypoxia as did the CAP amplitude (Figure 5f). Both followed the SpO₂ trace with an approximately ½ -minute delay, and also showed the slight overshoot (Figure 5d). The colored graphs in figure 5f indicate the CAP peak-to-peak amplitude at bias-tone phase positions indicated by the colored dots on the envelope in Figure 3f. Their order remained the same during the entire trace, indicating that the CAP modulation pattern did not change according to the OP shifts revealed by the DPs. The pattern just scaled in proportion to the SpO₂ level (with ½ -minute delay).

Two repetitions of this experiment after 1 and 3 hours and in the same ear revealed almost identical time courses. Qualitatively similar OP shifts were observed in the other 3 animals.

CONCLUSION

- The modulated DPs in the CM recordings are probably most reliable in determining the OP. Virtually no travel delay from origin to the RW gives modulation pattern according to the theory. But CM recordings are invasive.
- DPOAEs are an option when both 2f₁-f₂ and f₂-f₁ are recordable. But the latter is often too weak in human ears.
- Modulated DPOAEs provide good information, and just the modulated 2f₁-f₂ component might be sufficient to estimate the OP clinically in cases where both side-line pairs can be reliably collected.
- The dual-source of 2f₁-f₂ does not appear to cause problems (at least not at such high primary levels).
- Note that the relative phase between the 2f₁-f₂ and f₂-f₁ DPOAE modulation (Figure 3i) contradicts predicted inverse-proportionality. Their dips should be anti-phase like the CM pattern in Figure 3j. Varying the modulation frequency can reveal whether a difference in group delay coincidentally accounts for the apparently opposite phase.
- Modulated SFOAE were unsuitable for determining the OP. The overall amplitude of SFOAEs is, however, very sensitive to oxygenation and they follow the reduction of the CAP. In case that this observed covariance can be generalized, under certain circumstances, SFOAE might provide a non-invasive marker of variations in the neural output.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSIONS

[Anthony Gummer]: CAP measures, with stimulus intensities well above thresholds, are recruiting the low-frequency tails of neurons over a wide spatial range apical to the f2-place. It is possible that you don't observe operating point changes in the CAP modulation pattern because the part of CAP response that might indicate a shift is "swamped" by auditory nerve excitation outside the active region.

[Torsten Marquardt]: This is a good point, Tony! We must be careful with our conclusions here. It is possible that the CAP modulation pattern, evoked with stimuli closer to threshold, do change in accordance with the operating point shift seen with DPOAE. We can't, however, lower the stimulus level because the signal-to-noise ratio would get too low to obtain reliable patterns as there are only four stimulus onsets at each of the eight phase-positions within the biasing tone cycle.